

An Extreme Learning Machine Model for Growth Stages Classification of Rice Plants from Hyperspectral Images Subdistrict Indramayu

Nugroho Suhandono
Faculty of Computer Science
Universitas Indonesia
Depok, Indonesia
nugroho.suhandono@gmail.com

Febri Maspiyanti
Faculty of Computer Science
Universitas Indonesia
Depok, Indonesia
febri.maspi@ui.ac.id

Mohamad Ivan Fanany
Faculty of Computer Science
Universitas Indonesia
Depok, Indonesia
ivan@cs.ui.ac.id

Abstract

Hyperspectral images which consist of hundred spectrum bands is potentially used to construct forecasting system of rice stock reserve. The main issue is how to build classifier model which accurate as SVM and faster than conventional classification method as before. ELM is proposed as model classifier which must be improved to choose right activation function. In this paper, we evaluate a learning model which classifies rice plants growth stages from hyperspectral images without reducing the dimensionality of data based on ELM method which can produce accuracy capability as accurate as SVM but require less learning time, as proved by experimental result. We evaluate and compare the effectiveness of various different activation functions of ELM using kappa statistics to measure inter-rate agreement. And the highest accuracy achieve by classifier ELM using triangular basis function.

Keywords: extreme learning machine (ELM), activation function, hyperspectral, growth stages rice plants, classification.

I. INTRODUCTION

Remote sensing technology enables people to observe objects in a very large coverage areas. Recently, hyperspectral remote sensing is getting more popular and widely used in many research fields such as land cover usages [4] and agricultural information system [6]. Hyperspectral image provides very rich information and more potential for in-depth analysis and accurate decision making thanks to hundreds of spectrum bands that enables us to observe

and build inventory of natural resources such as agricultural stock inventory.

Remote sensing is important in providing real-time decision support for government and in designing sustainable food security policy. Despite the ability to observe and acquire critical information from wide coverage areas in real-time, at the same time, remote sensing technology also put up a challenging task to process such vast amount of data especially when the data is obtained from hyperspectral sensors.

However, data obtained from remote sensing should be processed first to become information which is ready for consumption by the policy makers. Machine learning is one of field which use data to processed or classified into crisp information which before used by government..

Many method in machine learning field can be used to classify hyperspectral data such as single angle mapper (SAM) [9], neural network [11] and support vector machine (SVM) [10]. These learning methods must preprocess the hyperspectral data to choose and rank an optimum number of bands composition. Principal component analysis is widely used to reduce the dimensionality [10-11]. This pre-processing strategy aims to gain computational efficiency and improve the accuracy. Due to its computational burden the preprocess, however, is not always necessary, such as an SVM scheme in [10] that the full data dimensionality capable to produce classification with accuracy as high as 97%.

Generally other learning methods [9-11] have the same goal to attain high accuracy in reasonable time. The complexity of classification algorithm, however, is becoming another reason why the computation is so hard and produces slow learning speed. Hence, the accuracy is important to prove that we have built a good and usable model, but the running time of learning speed is have to be our another consideration. Therefore, the author propose

to use a method which have accuracy capability as accurate as SVM and learning speed as faster than konvensional learning method before, that is Extreme Learning Machine (ELM).

Currently, research has begun to identify the phase growth stage of rice plants in order to predict the availability of rice stock in Indonesia via remote sensing observation of paddy field. An accurate and fast forecasting system to estimate the availability of rice stock is needed by government to get critical information for making policy. Related this issue, this paper is about to build classifier model using ELM methods.

II. LITERATURE STUDY

A. Multiclass Classification Problem

Basically, single-hidden layer feedforward neural networks (SLFNs) is method for classification of multiclass problem. As SLFNs, ELM can be applied in multiclass classification directly [2]. Details of multiclass for our case are growth stage of rice plant which has nine label classes. The label representation of level growth stage vegetative, reproductive and ripening which each that stage have three level that are early, middle and late. This class is based on information of IRRI [14].

B. Previous Study

Various classification methods developed and used to solve this problem. Curse of dimensionality on data hyperspectral is prime issue in the classification problem. The high dimensionality of the data makes it difficult to be classified. Therefore, a lot of research has been dedicated to develop a method that combines classification algorithms and feature extraction methods. One of them is in this paper [4] which combines genetic algorithm and principle component regression. That method can not only produce good accuracy with a low error rate but also capable to keep up degree of robustness. But this method of course requires a fairly high price for doing feature selection and prediction in one scheme, although the time needed to do prediction relative quickly due to the curse of dimensionality problem already solved.

Another solution is to use parallel computing resources [11] that allows us to compute more quickly than using ordinary computing resources such as PCs. But the main problem is not everyone and institution research has such computing resource. Interesting experiments in [10] compares several methods such as SVM, BackPropagation Neural Networks (BP-NN), and Maximum Likelihood Classification (MLC). SVM which does not require a pre-processing technique to reduce data dimensionality is able to produce better accuracy than the BP-NN and MLC. Method of SVM in this experiment used linier kernel, polynomial kernel, radial basis function (RBF) and

sigmoid kernel function. And the highest accuracy achieved by SVM using polynomial kernel and RBF.

Differed with our work. The limitations of computational resources by using ordinary PCs and the high complexity of dimensional data to be the reason why we chose to use ELM paper as you can read, we used Extreme Learning Machine method for classification in this paper. ELM also have reliability in accuracy as SVM, but the response speed of trained ELM is faster than SVM [15]. And the result of our experiment show highest accuracy achieved by ELM using triangular basis function as activation function.

III. METHODS

A. Extreme Learning Machine Method

Extreme Learning Machine usually called as Single-hidden layer feedforward networks. In this paper [1] is explained that this method capable to solve problem SLFNs conventional before, which are slow learning speed and local minima problem. Generally, this method is a mechanism learning for generalization SLFNs which this learning not necessary iterative tuning [2]. That's why learning speed of the ELM faster than SLFNs before.

figure 1. Structure of SLFNs

Based on the structure of single-hidden layer feedforward networks above, the mathematical modelling of extreme learning machine methods meets the following equation:

$$\sum_{i=1}^N \beta_i \cdot g(W_i \cdot X_j + b_i) = t_j \quad (1)$$

where :

$$j = 1, 2, \dots, N.$$

$w_i = (w_1, w_2, \dots, w_m)^T$, is the input weight vector.

$\beta_i = (\beta_1, \beta_2, \dots, \beta_m)^T$, is the output weight vector.

b_i , is threshold in hidden nodes.

$w_i x_j$, is inner product of w_i and x_j .

$g(x)$, is function of activation.

And for n arbitrary distinct samples, there is dataset samples (X_n, T_n) , where $X_n = \{X_1, X_2, \dots, X_n\}$ input samples and $T_n = \{T_1, T_2, \dots, T_n\}$ target samples.

The $\sum_{i=1}^N \beta_i \cdot g(W_i \cdot X_j + b_i) = t_j$; can be represented as

$$H \cdot \beta = T \quad (2)$$

Where:

$$H = (w_1, w_2, \dots, w_n; b_1, b_2, \dots, b_n; x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n)$$

$$= \begin{pmatrix} g(w_1 \cdot x_1 + b_1) & \dots & g(w_n \cdot x_1 + b_n) \\ \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ g(w_1 \cdot x_n + b_1) & \dots & g(w_n \cdot x_n + b_n) \end{pmatrix}$$

$$\beta = (\beta_1, \dots, \beta_n) \text{ and } T = (T_1, \dots, T_n)$$

Matrix H is usually called the hidden layer output matrix of neural network. Each element of this matrix will activate using activation function as written by $g(w_1 \cdot x_1 + b_1)$. The determination of input weights and biases, as discussed earlier become a differentiator with previous conventional methods of SLFNs. As we know the input weights and biases of ELM randomly determined without relying on any value. Meanwhile, to obtain the output weights (β), we can get from this equation $\beta = H^\dagger \cdot T$, where H^\dagger is Moore-Penrose inverse from hidden layer output matrix H .

Thus, it can be made in a simple algorithm which only consists of three phases as Huang propose [1] as follows:

- Specify the random input weights and hidden node biases.
- Calculate matrix H
- Calculate the output weights with moore-penrose rule for generalized inverse

B. Classifier Analysis

The problem when we built classifier model to predict classification issue is how we know the measurement of that model is capable to implementation. In this [13] explained that kappa statistic is one of solution to evaluate the model classifier. The scale of kappa is indicator value to represent that model is good enough or not. The kappa value can calculate using this formula:

$$\text{Kappa, } K = \frac{P_o - P_e}{1 - P_e} \quad (3)$$

Where:

P_o is observed agreement.

P_e is random agreement.

$P_o - P_e$ is agreement due to true concordance.

$1 - P_e$ is residual not random agreement.

$$P_o = \frac{\sum TP}{N} \quad (4)$$

$$P_e = \frac{\sum_1^n (P(a) * P(e))}{N^2}, \text{ where} \quad (5)$$

$\sum_1^n (P(a) * P(e))$ is dot product from *actual probability* dan *expectation probability* for each classes, given n number of classes and N is the number of data set.

Interpretation of kappa K which based on equation (3), can view in this below:

Kappa	Agreement
< 0	less than chance agreement
0.01–0.20	Slight agreement
0.21–0.40	Fair agreement
0.41–0.60	Moderate agreement
0.61–0.80	Substantial agreement
0.81–0.99	Almost perfect agreement (perfect)

While we compute kappa value, we can know about precision, sensitivity and specificity of each class based on ELM classifier using different activation function. The equation (6-8) is equation we used to get precision, sensitivity, and specificity of each class.

$$\text{Precision} = \frac{TP}{TP+FP} \quad (6)$$

$$\text{Sensitivity} = \frac{TP}{TP+FN} \quad (7)$$

$$\text{Spesificity} = \frac{TN}{TN+FP} \quad (8)$$

Where:

TP is true positif

TN is true negatif

FP is false positif

FN is false negative

IV. DATA, EXPERIMENTS AND RESULT

A. Data Experiments

The data we used in this research is a hyperspectral image of Subdistrict Indramayu, West Java, Indonesia. This image was captured using airborne HyMap sensor at the end of June 2008 during HyperSRI joint research project conducted by cooperation between Indonesia Agency for Assessment and Application of Technology (BPPT) and Japan Earth Remote Sensing Data Acquisition

Center (ERSDAC) as also used in this work [4]. This data, we divide into nine classes as rice growth phase based on IRRI [10]. That hyperspectral image which is consist of 116 bands, processed by taking each pixel and we get the total of 3935 dataset from all growth stage class. You can see the land cover of rice yield area according to our work by figure [2-3].

figure 2. Hyperspectral Image Subdistrict Indramayu

figure 3. Region of Interest Hyperspectral Image Subdistrict Indramayu

B. Experiments and Result

In the first experiment, we want to know the right function activation which giving good result as good accurate prediction of learning with ELM for this datasets. the function activate are sigmoid function, triangular basis function, sin function , hard limit function, and radial basis function by using some of hidden nodes is 20 nodes then we try running it during twenty times. We set expectation for getting testing accuracy is 75% as least accuracy. The accuracy we calculate using mean square error. We design the experiment as you can see in figure[4].

Figure 4. Flow diagram of experiments

This ELM experiments is implemented in Matlab while the preprocessing data were used ENVI and IDL programming [7] [8]. see figure [5-8,15] below for the accuracy and running time proceses.

Figure 5. Training Accuracy

In Figure 4 we can see that almost all the activation function has good accuracy above 79%, unless the activation function hardlim that there are still 65% accuracy.

Figure 6. Testing Accuracy

Testing accuracy can be seen at Figure 5, the result is not as good as training accuracy. Almost all the activation function used to produce accuracy is still below 75%, only a triangular basis function is always produces an accuracy above 70%

	Training Acc	Testing Acc
sigmoidal	0.80827	0.62315
triangular	0.85947	0.756345
sine	0.82222	0.632425
hardlim	0.67298	0.600965
radial	0.84916	0.689475

Table 1. Average Training and Testing Accuracy

The experiments done in twenty different variation of activation function, it seems that activation triangular basis function is the best average for training accuracy and testing accuracy, videlicet 85% and 75%. While the activation function hardlim still not getting good testing accuracy and training accuracy on average that are below 70%. But the testing accuracy sigmoidal activation function, sin function, and radial is still below 70%.

In carrying out the learning process ELM also need training time and testing time And figure [7] about the average of training time and testing time.

	Training Time	Testing Time
sigmoidal	0.19578	0.03354
triangular	0.1755	0
Sine	0.18096	0.00312
hardlim	0.20982	0.01872
Radial	0.20358	0.01404

Table 2. Average Training and Testing Time

For the average time to do any activation on learning ELM is different depend on what the function activation is used. Based on the result, ELM learning with triangular activation function takes the least role in a training and testing, videlicet 0.17 seconds for training and close to 0 seconds for testing.

Classes	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9
precision	0.88	0.79	0.65	0.96	0.93	0.71	0.39	0.87	0.59
Sensitivity	0.98	0.68	0.66	0.99	0.83	0.81	0.93	0.61	0.71
spesificity	0.98	0.97	0.95	1	0.99	0.96	0.95	0.98	0.97

Table 3. Function sigmoid evaluation

classes	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9
Precision	0.91	0.86	0.85	0.94	0.97	0.88	0.54	0.81	0.69
Sensitivity	0.95	0.82	0.85	0.99	0.88	0.91	0.86	0.66	0.7
spesificity	0.99	0.98	0.98	0.99	1	0.98	0.96	0.97	0.98

Table 4. Function triangular basis evaluation

classes	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9
Precision	0.85	0.76	0.64	0.94	0.9	0.78	0.52	0.84	0.55

From the results above, it is known that the ELM training using triangular activation function has the best performance among the others in term of both accuracy and learning speed which used for training and testing. So that activation function is used for subsequent experiments to see the influence of the number of hidden nodes used in the learning and it's performance by using ELM. Hidden nodes are used starting from 20 nodes to 1000 nodes to see the relationship between the number of hidden nodes and the result of a learning process with the ELM.

Figure 7. Training and Testing Accuracy

In experiments using a number of hidden nodes with different amounts, it appears that the training and testing accuracy ranging from about 20 to 1000 nodes will result in increasing the accuracy up to 92%. This shows that the greater number of hidden nodes are used, the higher the accuracy will be achieved.

Model classifier that we have used for the experiment, we evaluate by using kappa statistic which show the degree of inter-rater agreement. We also look at the level of precision, sensitivity, and spesificity of each class based on each activation function. For this experiment we used a hundred hidden-node. And the result can be seen in this table[9-13].

Sensitivity	0.93	0.69	0.68	0.97	0.89	0.76	0.9	0.63	0.67
spesificity	0.98	0.97	0.95	0.99	0.99	0.97	0.96	0.97	0.97

Table 5. Function sine evaluation

classes	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9
Precision	0.79	0.45	0.53	0.89	0.51	0.56	0.1	0.86	0.29
Sensitivity	0.81	0.67	0.58	0.78	0.71	0.46	0.78	0.41	0.42
spesificity	0.97	0.92	0.93	0.99	0.94	0.94	0.92	0.97	0.95

Table 6. Function hardlim evaluation

classes	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9
Precision	0.87	0.8	0.8	0.94	0.97	0.86	0.48	0.88	0.53
Sensitivity	0.97	0.75	0.77	1	0.89	0.88	0.91	0.63	0.69
spesificity	0.98	0.97	0.97	0.99	1	0.98	0.95	0.98	0.97

Table 7. Function radial basis evaluation

function	sigmoid	tribas	sine	hardlim	RBF
Model Accuracy	0.77	0.84	0.77	0.58	0.81
po	0.7687	0.8424	0.7726	0.5781	0.8145
pe	0.1192	0.1176	0.1186	0.1209	0.1191
po-pe	0.6496	0.7248	0.654	0.4573	0.6954
l-pe	0.8808	0.8824	0.8814	0.8791	0.8809
Cohen's kappa	0.7375	0.8214	0.742	0.5201	0.7894
degree of agreement	Substantial	Perfect	Substantial	Moderate	Substantial

Table 8. Function sigmoid evaluation

V. CONCLUSION AND DISCUSSION

Based on the result of experiment, ELM model classifier using triangular basis function is the most capable for built classifier model of classification growth stage rice yield, because triangular basis function can produce good testing accuracy as we expected. The highest learning speed of triangular basis function than others is reinforced for using it.

Actually we can view in figure[14] that the degree of accuracy depend on the number of hidden nodes. And the result evaluation in figure [9-14] show that the activation function using triangular is the best choice for built classifier using ELM, indeed.

Even though model can build using data without handle of curse dimensionality, its not mean pre-process not important. if we can pre-process data into optimum band choice and use this model, maybe we can get improvisation result and faster than model classifier before.

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